

Screening for Autism Spectrum Disorder using Modified Checklist for Autism in Toddlers, Revised with Follow up (MCHAT-R/F) Score**Deepkumar K. Patel^{1*}, Kamleshkumar G Rathod², Ketan Gadhavi³, Radhikaba Vaghela⁴, Bharat Muliya⁵**¹Junior Resident, Department of Pediatrics, C.U. Shah Medical College and Hospital, Surendranagar, Gujarat, India²Associate Professor, Department of Pediatrics, C.U. Shah Medical College and Hospital, Surendranagar, Gujarat, India⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Pediatrics, C.U. Shah Medical College and Hospital, Surendranagar, Gujarat, India^{3,5}Professor, Department of Pediatrics, C.U. Shah Medical College and Hospital, Surendranagar, Gujarat, India

Received: 28-06-2024 / Revised: 20-07-2024 / Accepted: 23-08-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Deepkumar Patel

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Introduction:** Autism spectrum disorder is a neurobiological disorder and its presentation can vary significantly from one individual to others. Early detection of ASDs can help in improving quality of child's life. Modified checklist for Autism in Toddlers, Revised with Follow up (MCHAT R/F) score is one of the screening tool to assess risk of Autism Spectrum Disorders.**Objectives:** To identify and classify Autism Spectrum Disorders using Modified checklist for Autism in Toddlers, Revised with Follow up (MCHAT R/F) score.**Methods:** This study was performed in all children aged between 16 to 30 months came in routine pediatric OPD in C.U. Shah Medical College, Surendra Nagar, Gujarat. MCHAT-R score was applied to all individuals and whenever required MCHAT R/F score was applied to get additional information.**Result:** Out of total 200 children, 176 children were found under low risk category and 3 were found in high risk category. While remaining 21 children came under medium risk. To whom MCHAT R/F score was applied and amongst them 1 child was found under high risk category, and according to categorisation appropriate actions were taken.**Conclusion:** As currently no any biomarkers were available for ASDs, MAHAT-R/F score is an effective tool to screen ASDs as early as possible and promote early interventions.

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Introduction

Autism spectrum disorder is a neurobiological disorder with onset in early childhood. [1] Today, ASDs have a prevalence of 62/10,000 globally. [2] In northwest India, the prevalence rate is 0.09/100 while it is 9.4% in South India. The key features are impairment in social communication and social interaction accompanied by restricted and repetitive behaviour. The presentation of Autism spectrum disorder can vary significantly from one individual to another, as well as over the course of development for a particular child. There is currently no biomarker for Autism spectrum disorder. Therefore accurate diagnosis requires careful review of the history and direct observation of child's behaviour.

Autism is a disorder that usually originates in infancy, mainly, in the first 3 years of life. According to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual

of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition, the required characteristics of ASD are persistent deficits of social communication and interaction; restricted and repetitive behaviours, interests, and activities. [2] The earliest signs of autism start appearing from 6 months onward. Autism is difficult to detect before 24 months but symptoms begin to show by 12–18 months. However, if the signs are detected as early as 18 months of age, early intervention can reduce the effects of the disorder. The signs and symptoms of ASD often go unnoticed by parents due to lack of awareness and profound ignorance leading to atypical development, motor disability, behavioural issues, and difficulties in activities of daily living. Most cases of autism have been diagnosed after the age of 4 years. Aggressive early intervention leads to the best long-term prognosis. [3] Early detection of ASDs can help in improving the quality of child's

life and support the child to lead a healthier lifestyle with this disorder. The present study intended to find the prevalence of ASD in children between 16–30 months using Modified Checklist for Autism in Toddlers, Revised with Follow-Up questionnaire.

The Modified Checklist for Autism in Toddlers, Revised with Follow-Up [4] is a 2-stage screening tool to assess risk for Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD). The M-CHAT-R/F can be administered and scored as part of routine O.P.D. and can also be used by other professionals to assess risk for ASD. The primary goal of the M-CHAT-R is to maximize sensitivity and detect as many cases of ASD as possible. The M-CHAT-R/F is designed to use for screening toddlers between 16 and 30 months of age to assess the risk for developing autism spectrum disorder (ASD). Even with the Follow-Up, a significant number of the children who fail the M-CHAT-R/F will not be diagnosed as ASD; but these children are at risk for other developmental disorders or delays and so follow-up is required for any child who screens positive in this test.

Aims and Objectives:

To identify and classify Autism Spectrum Disorder using Modified Checklist for Autism in Toddlers, Revised with Follow up (MCHAT-R/F) score.

Materials and Methods

This study was performed in all children aged between 16 to 30 months coming to routine Paediatrics OPD in C U Shah medical college.

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee. Children diagnosed with cerebral palsy, genetic disorders, mental retardation, congenital disorders, metabolic disorders and parents unwilling to participate in the study were excluded from the study. The principal investigator explained the purpose and the procedure of the study to the primary caretakers. A brief demographic data such as age and gender was recorded. The principal investigator asked MCHAT-R questionnaire to primary caretaker to record their responses related to their child's behaviour and the total score was calculated by the principal investigator. The MCHAT-R screening tool has 20 questions, where 1 point is given to each question. For all items except questions 2, 5, and 12, the response “NO” indicates ASD risk. The total score of 0–2 was considered as low risk whereas the medium risk score was 3–7 and high risk scores were 8–20. In medium risk, the Follow-Up (second stage of M-CHAT-R/F) was applied to get additional information about at-risk responses. In High risk situations, we immediately refer child for diagnostic evaluation and eligibility evaluation for early intervention.

Results:

In this study, majority of children were between age group of 28-30 months (40.5%) followed by age group between 16-19 months (23.5%) , 24-27 months (26%) and between 20-23 months (10%). Amongst all 58.5% were males and rest were females.

Table 1:

Age group (months)	Numbers
16-19	47
20-23	10
24-27	52
28-30	81

In the present study, on application of MCHAT-R score to all 200 children, 176 children scored between 0-2, which according to score were under low risk category. Three (3) children were found in high risk category whose scored between 8-20.

Graph : 1

Table : 2

Risk	Number
Low	176
Medium	21
High	3

Twenty one (21) children were in medium risk category who scored between 3-7, MCHAT-R/F score was applied to this 21 children. Amongst these 21 children 20 children were scored between 0-1, so they were included in low risk category and one (1) child was found in high risk category as he scored more than one in MCHAT-R/F score.

Graph: 2

Discussion

This study validates the M-CHAT-R/F, a 2-stage, level 1 ASD screening tool that requires little time and cost [5] to administer to toddlers attending 16 and 30 months. The recommended score classifies children into 3 risks on the basis of the MCHAT-R score. Children whose score suggests of low-risk range (88% of cases) do not need follow-up or further evaluation unless surveillance indicates ASD risk. Children should be rescreened if they are younger than 24 months, as recommended by the American Academy of Paediatrics. [6] Children whose scores are in the medium-risk range (10.5% of cases) require administration of the follow-up, which gathers further details about at-risk items. Children who score in the high-risk range (1.5% of cases) would directly refer to specialist rather than going into follow up. However, it is important to note that ASD screening continues to be challenging because no screening tool can have perfect sensitivity and specificity.

The performance of the M-CHAT-R/F was compared with the published studies using the M-CHAT/F in low-risk samples. [7] Overall, the revision significantly reduced the initial screen-positive rate, which means that fewer children require follow-up. One study of developmental screening showed paediatricians relying on clinical judgment alone missed 50% of children who went on to receive an ASD diagnosis. [8] A prevalence study was conducted in Kerala, India, using cluster random sampling and screened by community nurses on 6237 toddlers using the Modified Checklist for Autism in Toddlers –Revised (MCHAT-R) reported that toddlers at risk for ASD were 5.5% on MCHAT-R and on “Best Seven” was 2.7%. [9] In a cross-sectional survey of 11,000

So, out of total 200 children, 196 were found to be in low risk category and 4 were in high risk category at the end of study. Out of 4 high risk children all were males in present study.

Table : 3

Risk	Number
Low	196
High	4

children in the age group of 1–10 years using the Indian Scale for Assessment of Autism from the selected tribal, rural and urban areas of Himachal Pradesh, India, stated a prevalence of 0.9/1000 population and reported that ASD is a rare neurodevelopmental disorder as well as indicated SES as one of the fundamental indicators for ASDs in India. [10] As per present study, prevalence of the Autism spectrum disorder is 2%.

The current study also suggests that all high risks children were male suggesting male predominance nature of the disease.

As per present study, prevalence of the Autism spectrum disorder is 2%. It correlates with studies done in Asia, Europe and North America identified individuals with ASD with average prevalence of between 1 to 2%. [11]

Conclusion:

The M-CHAT-R/F is an effective tool to screen for ASDs. Integration of screening and surveillance strategies reduces the age of ASD diagnosis by 2 years, promoting early intervention and facilitating long-term prognosis.

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